

Characteristics of underwater cast and cured geopolymers

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ABSTRACT

Underwater cast and cured geopolymers with Si/Al ratios of 1.78 and 2.00, synthesized from Class C fly ash and metakaolin, were characterized by X-ray diffraction, X-ray fluorescence, scanning electron microscopy, and unconfined compression, to understand the interactions between the geopolymer slurry and curing saline solutions and pertinent effects on its strength development. Slurries of geopolymers and Class G oil well cement were cast into porous molds that were immediately submerged into 0, 15, and 35 ppt saline solutions for 28 days curing, during which the pH of curing solutions was monitored. While the oil well cement exhibits a decreased compressive strength in high-salinity solutions, the strength of the two geopolymers increases with the curing solution's salinity. The underlying mechanisms are the chemical exchanges between the curing solution and geopolymer slurry, particularly the leaching or ingress of alkali ions (e.g., Na⁺, OH⁻) via diffusion, which depends upon the curing solution's salinity.

1. Introduction

Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) is a typical, most widely used cementitious binder in the construction industry, owing to its excellent mechanical performance, adaptability, and affordability. On the other hand, the universal application of OPC also results in certain concerns, mainly including carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission, overconsumption of natural resources (e.g., limestone and clay), and high energy consumption in the manufacturing process. For example, producing one ton of OPC emits approximately one ton of CO₂ [1,2]. In fact, the Portland cement industry alone is responsible for approximately 5–7% of global carbon emissions [3,4]. Therefore, more environmentally-friendly cementitious materials with low or no CO₂ emissions are desired as a potential alternative to or at least partial replacement for OPC.

Another concern is the limitations or drawbacks of OPC's use in saline or chemically harsh environments. In the USA, Class G or H OPC is generally recommended by the American Petroleum Institute (API) as a cementing binder in deep wellbores and geo-sequestration sites, which both usually exist in brine formations. However, it has been

demonstrated by prior studies that there are potential concerns with the use of OPC in well cementing, such as degradation, lack of enough chemical (e.g., acid, saline, and sulfate) resistance, inadequate long-term durability, leakage, and strength reduction in high-salinity environments [5,6]. In fact, much work has been conducted to study the behavior of OPC in saline water. Suzuki et al. [7] studied the influence of NaCl on the calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) in OPC, and observed that Na⁺ is adsorbed on the surface of C-S-H, thus decreasing the Ca/Si molar ratio of C-S-H, and Cl⁻ accelerates the leaching of Ca in C-S-H. Lécolier et al. [8] found that the API Class G OWC samples first air-cured at a temperature of 80 °C and a pressure of 7 MPa for one month and then aged in fresh water and crude oil at the same temperature and pressure for one year don't show any obvious degradation in strength, while the counterparts aged in low-salinity water with a concentration of 0.4 mol/L and Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cl⁻, HCO³⁻, SO₄²⁻ as the major ions exhibit a 50% decrease in strength, because of the leaching of portlandite from the cement matrix. Zhou et al. [9] investigated the effects of 0–36 wt% NaCl solutions on the hydration of Class G OWC cured at 93 and 160 °C and 20.7 MPa, and their results showed that a low salt

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concentration accelerates hydration, while a high salt concentration impedes hydration. Besides, when the salt content is greater than 5 wt%, the cement's strength decreases with increasing salinity, due to the effect of NaCl on the leaching of Ca from C-S-H. In addition, sulfate corrosion is another important, well-studied issue. It is generally recognized that the reaction between cement hydration products and sulfate solution results in the formation of ettringite and gypsum, directly or indirectly leading to such destruction as expansion and cracking, which definitely causes softening, disintegration, and strength reduction [10,11]. Because of these serious concerns, investigating and developing new cementitious materials that are stronger, more durable, and more stable than the OPC is necessary and a focus of much existing research.

Because of its several key advantages over traditional OPC, such as low energy consumption for production and hence better sustainability, low carbon emission, and high durability, geopolymer, composed of SiO_4 and AlO_4 tetrahedra linked by sharing all the oxygen atoms to form a three-dimensional aluminosilicate structure [1,12,13], has been studied or recommended as a potential alternative to OPC and other cementitious binders, and may find plenty of viable applications in civil infrastructure and construction [14–17]. Geopolymerization is regarded as a complex process that generally consists of a series of reactions [18–21]: dissolution, reorientation, polycondensation, and solidification [1,14,22–24], which can overlap with each other and even take place almost simultaneously in the curing process. Although different source materials containing amorphous aluminosilicates can be used to synthesize geopolymer binders, fly ash and furnace slag have been widely used due to their comprehensive sources [25–27]. Metakaolin is another widely used raw material, which can improve the mechanical properties of geopolymer binders due to its high pozzolanic reactivity and finer particles [1,14,15].

To date, the durability of geopolymers cured in saline water has been studied to some extent. Lee and van Deventer [28] discovered that the durability of fly ash and metakaolin-based geopolymers is adversely influenced by different chlorides, possibly related to the hydrolytic attack on the primary aluminosilicate gel by Cl^- . Bakharev [29] examined the durability of fly ash-based geopolymers exposed to a 5 wt% sulfate solution, and found that the stability of the samples depends upon the types of used activators as well as the concentration and type of cations in the sulfate solution. Giasuddin et al. [30] studied the Class F fly ash-based geopolymers cured in fresh water, 8 and 15 wt% NaCl solutions at ambient temperature, and found that geopolymers cured in saline waters exhibit a higher strength than the counterparts cured in freshwater, but are still weaker than the air-cured ones. Their findings indicated that the degradation of strength is unlikely to be caused by the intrusion of salt into the sample, but rather the leaching of alkali and metal cations from the sample. Duan et al. [31] found that every type of studied geopolymer samples suffer the strength loss upon exposure to a 5 wt% sodium sulfate solution, and longer exposure causes worse performance in mechanical strength. They further noted that such deterioration mainly results from notable cracks, high porosity, and large pores.

As discussed above, curing geopolymers in saline solutions indeed causes certain negative influences on their mechanical properties. However, in these prior studies, the geopolymers subjected to curing or chemical attack in saline solutions had polycondensed and hardened or partially cured in air for certain durations. None of these studies has started with underwater casting or immediate curing in saline water, i. e., by submerging the geopolymer slurry immediately into saline water, which may allow the exchange of chemicals between the saline water and geopolymer slurry. In fact, if geopolymers were to be used in well cementing, then the precursor would need to be injected as a slurry into the well where chemical exchanges (e.g., ion transport, diffusion) between the geopolymer slurry and permeable rock formations take place before and during the polycondensation and subsequent curing processes. Inundating the partially pre-hardened or pre-cured geopolymer

samples in saline water fails to take into account the potential initial chemical reactions or exchanges between the slurry and surrounding environment (e.g., brine pore fluids from the rock formations), which may occur more rapidly in the slurry than the hardened cement. In summary, very little research has been conducted to study the effects of underwater casting and curing of geopolymer in saline solutions on its mechanical performance. The work presented in this paper is among the first to fill this gap, and its objective is two-fold: (1) to study the effects of casting and immediate curing in saline solutions on the characteristics of geopolymers in terms of mechanical properties, microstructure, and chemical and mineralogical compositions; (2) to investigate the effects of two different Si/Al molar ratios on the geopolymers' performance. In terms of novelty, this work used a commercial sea salt, but not pure chlorides or sulfates (e.g., NaCl or Na_2SO_4), to simulate the chemistry of brine fluids, and customer-built, porous, permeable molds for the underwater casting and curing of geopolymer slurry, which distinguishes this study from others that usually submerge pre-hardened geopolymer samples into saline solutions of varying concentrations.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

The raw materials selected for the synthesis of geopolymers consisted of Class C fly ash [32] (Headwater Resources, Inc., USA) and metakaolin (Advanced Cement Technologies, LLC, USA). Preliminary work found that the fly ash alone reacted too fast with the alkali activator solution, most likely due to the high CaO content in this Class C fly ash, leaving little to no time for handling and casting the geopolymer slurry into the curing molds. Therefore, to reduce the rate of geopolymerization reactions, metakaolin was added to the Class C fly ash at mass ratios of 1:5, 1:4, 1:3, and 1:1 to form the raw material mixtures, and it was found that the mass ratio of 1:1 yielded an appropriate reaction rate. Table 1 summarizes the chemical compositions and size fractions of the dry fly ash and metakaolin, while Fig. 1 shows their particle size distributions determined by the standard test method [33], with a median particle size (D_{50}) of 8.7 and 5.0 μm , respectively. In addition, for the purpose of comparison, Class G oil well cement (OWC) (LafargeHolcim, USA) was also studied in nearly all parallel testing. The activators included solid sodium hydroxide with a >95% purity quotient (Fisher Scientific, Inc., USA) and sodium silicate solution (Fisher Scientific, Inc., USA) with a specific gravity of 1.4, consisting of 9.1 wt% Na_2O , 29.2 wt% SiO_2 , and 61.7 wt% H_2O .

In addition, a synthetic Instant Ocean sea salt (Spectrum Brands, Inc., USA) was used to prepare artificial saline water to simulate natural seawater or brine solutions, because prior studies concluded that this commercial salt provides the necessary cations and anions at concentrations closest to those of the natural ocean water [34]. In descending

Table 1
Size fractions and chemical compositions^a of the Class C fly ash and metakaolin.

Composition	Class C Fly ash (wt.%)	Metakaolin (wt.%)
Clay-sized fraction ($\leq 2 \mu\text{m}$)	14.70	38.30
Silt-sized fraction (2–75 μm)	74.10	58.90
Sand-sized fraction ($>75 \mu\text{m}$)	11.20	2.80
SiO_2	38.56	56.61
Al_2O_3	19.80	39.16
Fe_2O_3	6.26	1.87
MgO	5.15	0.09
CaO	22.28	0.05
SO_3	1.72	0.05
K_2O	0.61	0.30
Na_2O	1.58	0.01
Moisture	0.11	0.13
LOI	0.41	0.19
Total	96.48	98.46

^a Chemical composition data were provided by the suppliers.

Fig. 1. Particle size distribution of the two raw materials, fly ash and metakaolin, used for geopolymer synthesis.

order, this salt contains Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} as major cations, and Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , TCO_2 (total CO_2) and HCO_3^- as major anions. Since the highest salinity of natural ocean water is 35 ppt (parts per thousand), three different salinities, 0, 15, and 35 ppt, were used for the curing of geopolymer slurry.

Three kinds of split cylindrical molds were manufactured for the curing of geopolymer slurry under different conditions (Fig. 2):

- Type I: non-porous acrylic (or plexiglass) split molds of 2.0×5.0 cm in inner diameter and height were used to cure geopolymer slurry in air (i.e., air curing);
- Type II: split high-density polyethylene (HDPE) molds of 3.81 cm (or 1.5 inch) in inner diameter and 8.89 cm (or 3.5 inch) in height with porous side walls of $10 \mu\text{m}$ in pore size were used to cure geopolymer slurry with a Si/Al ratio of 1.78 in saline water;
- Type III: split HDPE molds of 2.54 cm (or 1.0 inch) in inner diameter and 6.35 cm (or 2.5 inch) in height with porous side walls of $10 \mu\text{m}$ in pore size were used to cure geopolymer slurry with a Si/Al ratio of 2.00 in saline water.

The Type I non-porous molds were used to air-cure geopolymers with an aim to avoid rapid water loss from the geopolymer slurry during curing. To simulate the field conditions of underground oil wells where the cement slurry is injected between the steel casing and well wall (i.e., usually permeable rocks), porous molds (i.e., Types II and III) are preferred, since they permit possible chemical exchanges and even fluid flow between the curing chemical solutions and geopolymer slurry. HDPE was chosen because it is highly stable and does not react with the chemicals in the curing solutions or geopolymer slurry. With respect to the dimensions, Type II molds resulted in relatively larger geopolymer samples that require a high-capacity loading frame for unconfined compression testing. Therefore, the relatively smaller Type III molds were also manufactured so that unconfined compression testing could be performed in a low-capacity loading frame. Nevertheless, all three types of molds maintained an aspect ratio (i.e., height to diameter ratio) of 2.3–2.5 to minimize the end effects encountered in unconfined compression testing. For each mold, the two end caps were non-porous or impermeable and were made of polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), which is also highly resistant to chemicals such as acid, alkali, and salt (Fig. 2).

2.2. Geopolymer syntheses

All of the studied geopolymers were pre-designed to have two different Si/Al molar ratios of 1.78 and 2.00, hereafter designated as “GC-1.78” and “GC-2.00” respectively, because prior work [35] showed

that these two Si/Al ratios can result in geopolymers with relatively high strength. The activator solutions all had the same $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{O}$ molar ratio of 2.0, resulting in two final geopolymers: (1) GC-1.78: Si/Al ratio = 1.78, Na/Al ratio = 0.45; (2) GC-2.00: Si/Al ratio = 2.00, Na/Al = 0.67.

Geopolymer slurry was prepared by mixing the dry powder mixture of raw materials, consisting of fly ash and metakaolin at a mass ratio of 1:1, with the activator solution at a mass ratio of 1:2. The latter was prepared by dissolving solid NaOH in deionized water, followed by adding the sodium silicate solution at the pre-designed $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{O}$ molar ratio of 2.0. After thorough mixing for at least 5 min, the activator solution was allowed to cure overnight in a sealed container. On the next day, the fly ash and metakaolin mixture was added to the activator solution, followed by mixing for a minimum of 15 min to ensure complete mixing and to facilitate the raw material-activator reactions, resulting in the formation of geopolymer slurry.

The aforementioned three types of split molds were then used to form cylindrical samples for mechanical testing. For the non-porous Type I molds, a thin layer of vacuum grease was applied to the inner surfaces of the mold and two end caps to facilitate the subsequent removal of the cured geopolymer samples. For the two types of porous molds, a layer of pre-wetted Whatman filter paper with a nominal pore size of $20 \mu\text{m}$ was inserted inside the molds and seamlessly and conformedly attached to its inner wall to facilitate subsequent removal of completely cured samples and to prevent clogging of the mold’s porous walls. In addition, the filter paper still permitted chemical exchanges between the geopolymer slurry and curing solution. To achieve better sealing of the two end caps, a thin layer of plastic film was also used between the cap and the two split half cylinders (Fig. 2).

The GC-2.00 geopolymer slurry was casted into the pre-assembled Type III molds, followed by hand-vibrating to remove trapped air, then the top cap was fastened to seal the top of the cylindrical mold. Then, the assembled molds filled with geopolymer slurry were immediately immersed in different saline solutions for curing in the ambient laboratory environment. The GC-1.78 slurry was casted in Type II molds. In addition to saline water curing, part of the slurry from each of the two geopolymers was also casted in Type I molds, followed by curing in air. Three different salinities, 0, 15, and 35 ppt, were used to cure the geopolymer slurry. For each salinity, a group of 4 identical samples were cured for 28 days, resulting in a total of $2 \times 3 \times 4 = 24$ samples cured in saline solutions and a total of $2 \times 4 = 8$ samples cured in air. At the same time, the OWC slurry mixed at a water to cement mass ratio of 0.5 was also prepared in the same curing conditions, resulting in 12 samples cured in solutions and 4 samples cured in air.

To facilitate the subsequent estimation of chemical exchanges between the curing solutions and the OWC and geopolymer samples, a constant volume (i.e., 150 mL) of saline solutions was used for curing each sample in a 500 mL beaker, which was completely sealed by Parafilm to prevent evaporation or water loss during the entire curing process. As such, the concentrations of different chemicals could be accurately determined. After 28 days of curing, all samples were retrieved from the curing solutions and de-molded, followed by air-drying for a minimum of 7 days before mechanical testing, chemical analysis, and microstructure characterization.

2.3. Mechanical, microstructural, and chemical characterization

For mechanical characterization, unconfined compression tests [36] were performed on the cured and air-dried GC-1.78 samples using an MTS loading frame (with a load capacity of 100,000 lb) in the Piece Laboratory at Massachusetts Institute of Technology at a recommended loading rate of 0.25 ± 0.05 MPa/s, while a Geotest loading frame with a load capacity of 10,000 lb was used to measure the unconfined compressive strength of GC-2.0 and OWC at a constant strain rate of 0.5%/min. While both loading frames were installed with off-specimen (i.e., set up on the frame, but not in direct contact with the specimen) linear voltage displacement transducers (LVDTs), the MTS machine also

Fig. 2. Split molds made of porous HDPE cylinders: (a) a completely disassembled mold showing the two split half cylinders and two end caps; (b) a fully assembled mold fastened by a clamp; (c) partially assembled molds that are ready for geopolymer slurry casting. Note that a layer of plastic film is inserted between the end cap and cylinder end for better sealing.

included two on-specimen displacement sensors called alternating current displacement transducers (ACDTs) for more accurate small-strain measurements. The two ends of each sample were re-capped with the plaster of Paris, followed by correcting and polishing with sandpaper and level gauges to ensure perpendicularity between the sample's end surfaces and cylindrical axis. In addition, a very thin layer of lubricant coating was applied to the two ends of each sample in order to minimize the friction and pertinent shear stress development between the specimen's end surfaces and stainless-steel end platens of the loading frame.

The micromorphology and microstructure of the raw materials (including both fly ash and metakaolin) and the cured GC-2.00 samples were characterized in a Neoscope JCM-5000 scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JEOL, Ltd., Japan) using an accelerating voltage of 10 kV, while the cured GC-1.78 samples were examined in a high-resolution FEI Magellan 400 XHR SEM (FEI Company). Different pieces retrieved from both the interior core and exterior layer of the GC-2.00 cylindrical

samples were examined separately, while only the interior of the GC-1.78 samples was studied. For SEM characterization, all examined samples were sputter-coated by a thin layer of gold.

Further chemical and mineralogical analyses were conducted by X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) and X-ray diffraction (XRD), respectively. Both X-ray-based techniques require finely-ground powder samples. Thus, the cured geopolymer samples were wet ground with isopropyl alcohol, which acted as a lubricant and buffer to preserve the atomic structure of some delicate crystals [37], in a McCrone micronizing mill for 2 min, which usually produces a fine powder with particle sizes of $\leq 45 \mu\text{m}$. Elemental analysis was performed on the fine powders in a Siemens MRS 400 MP and a Philips PW2400 XRF spectrometer. The mineralogical composition of fly ash, metakaolin, and cured geopolymer samples were characterized using a Philips X'Pert-MPD diffractometer, and the random powder sample mount was prepared by the razor-tamped surface (RTS) method [35], which can minimize preferred

orientation of platy particles such as clays in the sample mount. All XRD scans used Cu K α radiation, a step size of 0.02 $^\circ$, a scan speed of 0.02 $^\circ$ per second, and a scan range of 15–55 $^\circ$ 2 θ (diffraction angle). The exchange of ions, particularly OH $^-$, between the geopolymer slurry and the curing saline solutions, was also monitored by measuring the change in pH of the curing solutions before the placement of geopolymer samples and at the end of 28-day's curing (i.e., the completion of curing), using a SevenCompact S220 pH meter (Mettler-Toledo, LLC., Columbus, OH, USA), which was pre-calibrated by standard buffer solutions of pH 4.00, 7.00, and 10.00.

3. Analysis of results

3.1. Compositional analysis by XRD

Fig. 3a presents the XRD patterns of GC-1.78 samples cured in three different saline solutions, while Fig. 3b shows those for the two raw materials, Class C fly ash and metakaolin, and the GC-2.00 samples

cured at different conditions (i.e., including curing in air and curing in three saline solutions). In general, fly ash and metakaolin are mainly composed of amorphous aluminosilicates, which are manifested in their XRD patterns. In fact, there is a broad hump between 20 and 36 $^\circ$ 2 θ in the XRD pattern of fly ash, and metakaolin shows a pronounced broad hump between 15 and 35 $^\circ$ 2 θ . In addition, as indicated by the sharp reflections, the crystalline phases, some of which also superimpose on the broad hump, are present as impurities in the raw materials: the fly ash contains quartz, mullite, calcite, hematite, and magnetite, while quartz, mullite, and magnetite are present in the metakaolin. As discussed later, these crystalline phases are non-reactive, and hence are present as impurities or solid fillers in the cured geopolymer.

For all GC-1.78 and GC-2.00 samples cured in different saline solutions, a pronounced broad hump between 15 and 40 $^\circ$ 2 θ , which is the characteristic reflection or peak of the amorphous or short-range ordered structure of geopolymers [13,30,38], is present in all XRD patterns. Overall, there are not too many obvious differences between the XRD patterns of the two types of geopolymers cured in the same salinity as well as the same kind of geopolymers cured in different salinities. In addition, some sharp reflections are also present, which are clearly inherited from the crystalline phases in the two raw materials, further validating that the crystalline phases are not involved in geopolymerization reactions and are hence present as inert fillers in the geopolymer binder. This is consistent with the popular standpoint that only amorphous phases in the raw materials are reactive and contribute to geopolymerization [21,38,39]. These results also prove that the cured end products are not purely amorphous but include crystalline phases as impurities and inclusions.

3.2. Mechanical properties

Fig. 4 shows some typical unconfined compression stress-strain curves selected from the two geopolymers cured in different saline solutions. For the purpose of comparison, some OWC stress-strain curves are also included. Some curves show a much softer response and hence much smaller initial Young's modulus at the beginning section, and the three OWC specimens exhibit a much more severe response. During the demolding of the 28 day-cured specimens, it was observed that the OWC specimens showed significantly higher shrinkage deformation than the geopolymer counterparts, and hence required more plaster to re-cap the ends. Because the plaster is usually softer and weaker than the OWC and geopolymer, the initial soft response is primarily caused by the deformation of the plaster. A secondary cause is the deformation of the lubricant coating applied to the specimen's end to reduce friction as well

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of raw materials and geopolymer samples cured in different saline solutions: (a) GC-1.78; (b) GC-2.00 (MK = metakaolin, CFA = Class C fly ash, Mu = Mullite, Ca = Calcite, He = Hematite, M = Magnetite, Q = Quartz).

Fig. 4. Example stress-strain curves of Class G oil well cement and geopolymer samples.

as any non-conformed contacts between the specimen and load platens. All curves show a well-defined linear elastic regime, but the yielding is poorly defined. Moreover, these curves show the obvious characteristics of brittle failure typically observed in cementitious materials such as geopolymers and OPC. A few curves show a non-linear elastic regime, most likely caused by the misalignment due to the samples' imperfect end surfaces. Nevertheless, the fundamental mechanical properties, such as peak strength, Young's modulus, and failure strain, of these samples can be obtained from their respective stress-strain curves.

Fig. 5a compares the UCS of all three different types of samples (i.e., OWC, GC-1.78, and GC-2.00) cured in different conditions. The OWC has the highest UCS of 63.16 ± 1.28 MPa under pure (i.e., 0 ppt salinity) water curing, proving that this cement can work well under freshwater casting and curing, while much lower UCSs of 54.95 ± 8.26 and 45.40 ± 1.82 MPa are obtained when the OWC is cured at 15 and 35 ppt saline solutions. The lowest OWC UCS of 37.75 MPa is obtained from air-curing, most likely due to the fact that the original cement-to-water ratio (which was provided by the OWC vendor) used to prepare the cement slurry is designed for direct in-water curing (e.g., casting and curing in underground oil wells). Another possible reason is that the OWC slurry cured in fresh and saline waters absorbs more water to achieve better hydration reactions for strength development. Overall, the UCS of OWC obviously decreases with increasing the curing solutions' salinity, with the maximum reduction of 28.1% at 35 ppt salinity. These results point to the definitive, negative effects of saline water curing on the strength development of OWC, and uncovering the underlying mechanisms requires further analysis of some possible complicated chemical reactions or exchanges between the cement slurry and curing solutions.

However, the opposite is observed for the GC-1.78 and GC-2.00 geopolymer samples cured in the same conditions. For the GC-1.78, an increase in the salinity of curing solutions causes a continuous increase in the UCS: from 31.50 ± 1.61 to 39.93 ± 1.18 and then to 49.87 ± 5.15 MPa for 0, 15, and 35 ppt respectively. A similar trend is also observed for the GC-2.00, although in general the GC-2.00 is stronger than GC-1.78 in general. Compared to the UCS obtained from the 0 ppt curing solution, the maximum increase in the UCS for GC-1.78 and GC-2.00 are 58.3% and 27.8%, respectively, with the former having an even higher percentage of increment. A noteworthy difference between the two geopolymers is that the UCS (i.e., 29.25 MPa) of air-cured GC-1.78 is lower than that of those cured in water or saline solutions, while that of GC-2.00 (i.e., 56.67 MPa) is higher than that of those cured in 0 ppt solution but less than that of those cured in saline solutions. This indicates that, compared to samples cured in freshwater, air-curing or dry-curing (i.e., without allowing chemical reactions or exchanges between the geopolymer slurry and curing solutions) in a non-porous mold has little influence on the GC-1.78 UCS, but results in a higher UCS for GC-2.00.

Fig. 5b–d compares the failure strain, Young's modulus, and bulk density of all samples, respectively. For the GC-1.78, the greatest failure strain (1.48%) and Young's modulus (5.43 GPa) occur at 35 and 15 ppt, respectively, while for the GC-2.00 the failure strain increases with the salinity. The large failure strains are somewhat affected by the artefact that the initial softer response of certain stress-strain curves (e.g., OWC, Fig. 4) may contribute an extra 0.1–0.2% strain to the measured failure strains where such an extra strain could be removed. In general, at the same curing salinity, the GC-2.00 samples exhibit higher failure strains than the GC-1.78, indicating that the GC-2.00 can sustain larger strain or deformation before failure. Moreover, the failure strains of the two geopolymers are all greater than those of OWC, indicating that the two geopolymers may perform better in terms of resistance to tensile cracking if these materials are assumed to behave isotropically (i.e., the stress-strain-strength behavior is the same for both tension and compression or other loading directions). In fact, some research [40] found that there is a relative stable proportional relationship between tensile and compressive strengths of geopolymers.

The more ductile behavior of the studied geopolymers can be further demonstrated by the fact that their Young's moduli are all smaller than those of OWC (Fig. 5c). In fact, the Young's modulus of GC-2.00 decreases with increasing salinity. Overall, saline-water curing appears to make the OWC weaker and more brittle, while the opposite occurs for the two geopolymers. Even more, the GC-2.00 can become stronger and more ductile than the GC-1.78 in the 35 ppt curing solution. According to some published work [41,42], the Young's modulus of OWC cured for 14 and 20 days is nearly 12 and 14 GPa, respectively, which agree well with those of the underwater cast and cured OWC. The relatively lower elastic modulus of the air-cured OWC (e.g., <6 GPa) obtained in this study may be caused by the fact that the adopted design mix (e.g., water to cement ratio) is developed for underwater casting and curing, but not for air-curing. Also, previous work [21,38] also found that the Young's modulus of fly ash and metakaolin-based geopolymers is indeed lower than that of ordinary Portland cement. This observation also agrees well with the lower elastic modulus of the geopolymers reported in this paper.

Finally, the bulk density of OWC decreases slightly with increasing the curing solution's salinity, but is still much greater than those of the two geopolymers (Fig. 5d). However, saline water curing causes little influence on the bulk density of the two geopolymers, and the GC-2.00 has a slightly higher bulk density than the GC-1.78. In general, a structural material with a lower bulk density but higher UCS can bring multiple benefits to the design and construction, such as smaller dead loads but higher resistance. Also noteworthy is the fact that some applications require more ductile cementitious materials such as oil well cementing or structural members under tensile loading. While most structural materials require both high strength and high stiffness, developing certain materials with a lower Young's modulus but without sacrificing high failure strength is desired by some industries.

3.3. Microstructure

Knowledge of the micromorphological characteristics (e.g., particle size and shape) of the raw materials helps in the recognition and identification of the microstructure and composition of the final, completely-cured geopolymeric products, such as the presence of unreacted or partially reacted phases by observing their size and geometry. Fig. 6 compares the micromorphological features of the two raw materials. The fly ash particles generally occur as microspheres of $\sim 1\text{--}20$ μm in diameter (Fig. 6a). In fact, fly ash generally consists of three kinds of spheres: solid spheres, hollow spheres, and cenospheres [43]. As discussed later, all three kinds of spheres can be observed in the studied geopolymer samples. In contrast, the majority of metakaolin particles (Fig. 6b) are platy in shape, which is inherited from its parent material, platy kaolinite crystals, while some aggregates of 10–30 μm in size can also be observed. It appears that, although calcination of kaolinite at higher temperatures (e.g., >450–850 °C) causes dehydroxylation and hence partial or complete collapse of its crystal structure, metakaolin particles may still maintain their platy shape.

Fig. 7 is an example SEM micrograph selected to show the overall microstructure and major constituents of the cured geopolymer, illustrating the multiphase nature of the final geopolymer products. According to a previous study [38], the final geopolymer products are actually a multiphase composite consisting mainly of unreacted fly ash and metakaolin particles, partially reacted fly ash and metakaolin particles, neo-formed geopolymer binder, and non-reactive impurities such as crystalline quartz and hematite inherited from the raw materials. In addition, randomly distributed spherical micropores, cavities, and microcracks can be observed. In general, these pores are likely introduced into the sample by two possible sources: (1) residual air bubbles that are entrapped into the geopolymer slurry during mixing and casting, and (2) the space that is previously occupied by water droplets (due to insufficient mixing) but then becomes a void after water evaporates. In fact, prior work points out that the presence of macroscale pores in

Fig. 5. Mechanical and physical property indexes of Class G oil well cement and geopolymer cement samples after 28 days curing: (a) unconfined compressive strength; (b) failure strains; (c) Young's modulus; (d) bulk densities (The error bars represent one standard deviation, which applies to other figures as well).

Fig. 6. SEM micrographs of raw materials: (a) Class C fly ash; (b) metakaolin.

Fig. 7. An SEM micrograph showing the overall microstructure and composition of the geopolymer samples.

geopolymers is not unusual [44]. Microcracks may also have two potential origins: (1) shrinkage cracks created upon water evaporation during the process of geopolymer curing and air-drying, and (2) loading-induced cracks created during the unconfined compression testing. These microstructural defects, including micropores and

microcracks, can have a detrimental influence on the mechanical performance of geopolymers.

Fig. 8 shows selected SEM micrographs of the GC-1.78 samples cured in 0, 15, and 35 ppt saline solutions. All samples, regardless of the curing conditions, consist of unreacted and partially-reacted components within the fully reacted, neo-formed geopolymer binder as the major matrix. At this length scale, there is not too much of a difference in the general bulk microstructure among the different samples cured in different salinities. Therefore, understanding of the origin of different mechanical properties among these samples warrants further compositional and chemical analyses of these materials, which is discussed in the next two sections.

After the UCS measurements, careful examination of the cross-sectional surfaces of failed cylindrical samples found that the color of the exterior layer is usually lighter than that of the interior layer for all the tested samples. Therefore, the microstructure and composition of the exterior and interior layers are worth separate discussion and comparison. As an example, Fig. 9 compares the different visual appearances and microstructures of the exterior and interior layers of a 15 ppt saline water-cured GC-2.00 sample. Clearly, on the cross-sectional surfaces (Fig. 9a–b), the interior core is darker than the exterior layer, even

Fig. 8. SEM micrographs of the GC-1.78 cured in saline water: (a) 0 ppt; (b) 15 ppt; (c) 35 ppt.

Fig. 9. Different appearance and microstructure of the exterior and interior layers of 15 ppt saline water-cured GC-2.00 samples: (a) and (b) optical images of the cross-sectional surface of two different cylindrical samples; (c) SEM micrograph of the exterior layer; (d) SEM micrograph of the interior layer.

though the change is transitional and progressive, and the boundary is not so well defined. Moreover, the circular boundary of color transition indicates that the radial change takes place starting from the outermost cylindrical surface of the samples. Fig. 9c–d presents two typical SEM micrographs of the exterior layer and interior core of the same sample. Surprisingly, some pores of 80–400 μm in diameter are present in both the interior and exterior layers. However, it appears that the exterior layer contains relatively larger pores than the interior layer, mostly likely due to the fact that the exterior layer has direct contact with the curing solution and thus allows water to seep or permeate into this part of the geopolymer slurry before it hardens.

Fig. 10 presents the SEM micrographs of the GC-2.00 samples cured in 0, 15, and 35 ppt saline solutions at much higher magnifications. Again, the interior and exterior layers are separated and compared in this figure. First of all, it appears that the exterior layer has relatively more unreacted or partially reacted components and more pores embedded in the neo-formed matrix. In contrast, the interior has a fairly homogeneous and continuous matrix with more reacted components. Among the samples cured in different salinities, higher salinities (e.g., 15 and 35 ppt) tend to generate a more homogeneous matrix with a larger fraction of reacted binder when compared to the sample cured in freshwater. The homogeneous and continuous matrix reflects the formation of the geopolymer binder that contributes to the improved UCS. Overall, the saline solutions have a larger influence on the exterior than the interior of the samples, which is consistent with the pictures shown in Fig. 9a–b. In addition, other typical features include the presence of randomly distributed micro-pores and micro-cracks in all samples, with the majority of cracks occurring around pores and unreacted fly ash particles that obviously have weaker adhesion with, or are relatively weaker, than the neo-formed geopolymer binder.

In Fig. 11, selected SEM micrographs show the different micromorphological features of residual fly ash particles in the geopolymer binder. In Fig. 11a, an unreacted, broken hollow sphere of fly ash

particles of 25–30 μm in size can clearly be seen, while Fig. 11b shows a large cenosphere that is filled with many smaller spheres of unreacted fly ash particles. In general, completely reacted fly ash particles should fully dissolve and then transform into a homogeneous geopolymer binder. However, in the hardened geopolymer binder, fly ash particles may be partially reacted and thus maintain their spherical geometry. Fig. 11c shows a solid spherical fly ash particle that has partially dissolved and reacted, leaving some empty space inside the spherical boundary. In addition, part of the external surface is still smooth, while the other part has been replaced with rough and granular stuffing, indicating that this particle is definitely partially dissolved and reacted. Fig. 11d shows a completely reacted fly ash particle, but the fly ash-to-geopolymer transformation has not advanced to the point where the reacted particle no longer maintains its spherical geometry. Moreover, it seems that the surface of the reacted sphere is highly porous, which is likely an indicator of the early termination of the ongoing geopolymerization reaction (e.g., possibly before the settling or hardening of geopolymer precursor). In addition, in all four micrographs, some smaller spheres that may be the unreacted fly ash particles can also be identified. These observations indicate that the final geopolymer products may not conform to the pre-designed Si/Al ratios, owing to a small fraction of raw materials not involved in the reaction. In fact, the change in the Si/Al molar ratio as well as the reduction in the relative content of pure geopolymer binder can directly affect the development of the UCS.

3.4. X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis

In general, XRF yields the mass percentages of the compositional elements in a material, which are then by convention converted to the corresponding oxides, such as SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 , TiO_2 , MnO , CaO , Na_2O , K_2O , and P_2O_5 , among others. Based on the elements' percentages, the average Si/Al molar ratios of all geopolymer samples cured in different saline solutions were calculated, and the results are presented

Fig. 10. SEM micrographs of the GC-2.00 samples cured in different saline water: (a–b) 0 ppt; (c–d) 15 ppt; (e–f) 35 ppt; (a), (c), and (d) are from the exterior layer; (b), (d), and (f) are from the interior.

in Table 2. For the GC-1.78 samples, the Si/Al molar ratio decreases from 1.83 to 1.79 when the salinity increases from 0 to 35 ppt. When compared with the air-cured samples, underwater casting and curing tends to increase the Si/Al ratio. For the air-cured GC-2.00 sample, the actual Si/Al ratio measured by XRF is 1.98, slightly lower than the pre-designed value of 2.00, which may be caused by the variability and nonhomogeneity of the raw materials. Similarly, underwater casting and curing causes an increase in the Si/Al ratio: i.e., 1.99 for 0 ppt, 2.09 for 15 ppt, and 2.04 for 35 ppt. The increase in the Si/Al ratio in the immediate water-cured samples suggests that a loss of Al^{3+} may have taken place, or the Al^{3+} may migrate from the geopolymer slurry into the curing solutions. At this time, it is unclear why the Si^{4+} does not migrate out of the slurry. Nevertheless, the amount of lost Al^{3+} is still very small when compared with other cations, as discussed later.

As an example to illustrate the occurrence of chemical exchanges between the curing solutions and the geopolymer slurry that is being cured, Fig. 12 compares various Si-based elements' concentrations (i.e., in terms of the molar ratio of a specific element to Si) for the GC-2.00 sample cured in fresh water. For all of the considered major elements, including Si, Al, Na, Fe, Mg, Ca, and K, a dramatic decrease in the Na/Si

ratio occurs, indicating that the major chemical exchange is the loss of Na^+ , i.e., the permeation of the Na^+ from the geopolymer slurry to the curing solution, while other elements have little loss. Moreover, the exterior layer of the sample experiences more Na^+ loss than the interior core, which should be expected. In fact, since the curing mold is permeable, the slurry that is being cured, which has a much higher Na^+ concentration than the curing fresh water, loses its Na^+ via mainly diffusion induced by differential concentration. However, upon immediate submersion of the slurry into water, the geopolymerization reaction (mainly the polycondensation or hardening stage) occurs at the same time as the chemical exchange between the being-cured geopolymer slurry and curing solution, thus competing with the diffusion process to retain the Na^+ . If the geopolymerization occurs very fast, leaving little time to allow the migration or diffusion of Na^+ out of the slurry, then the majority of Na^+ cations remains in the cured geopolymer. This is mainly the case for the interior core of the sample. On the contrary, a slow geopolymerization reaction allows more Na^+ to leach into the curing water, which is the case for the exterior layer of the sample. As such, future research may investigate the kinetics of the two competing reactions: chemical exchange or diffusion versus

Fig. 11. SEM micrographs showing the different micromorphological features of fly ash particles: (a) unreacted hollow sphere; (b) unreacted cenosphere; (c) partially reacted solid sphere; (d) completely reacted solid sphere.

Table 2
The average Si/Al molar ratios of all geopolymer samples cured in different saline solutions.

Curing solution concentration (ppt)	Si/Al molar ratio	
	GC-1.78	GC-2.00
0	1.83	1.99
15	1.81	2.09
35	1.79	2.04
Air-curing	1.78	1.98

Fig. 12. The elemental composition of the GC-2.00 sample cured in fresh water.

geopolymerization.

Prior discussion indicates that a major change in the Na/Si ratio occurs in the water-cured samples. As such, in the subsequent analysis, only Na or Na₂O is selected as an effective indicator to assess the degree of chemical exchanges between the being-cured geopolymer slurry and the curing saline solutions. Fig. 13a compares the mass-based Na₂O contents for the two geopolymer samples cured in different saline solutions. Again, for the GC-2.00 samples, results of the exterior layer and interior core are separate in this figure. In general, for both types of geopolymers, the Na₂O content increases with increasing the salinity of the curing solutions. Moreover, for the GC-2.00 samples, the Na₂O content of all the exterior layers is less than that of the interior core, which is consistent with the visually observed color change (Fig. 9a and b). When compared with the air-cured GC-2.00 sample, the interior layer of the 35 ppt cured sample possesses an even higher Na₂O content than the air-cured counterpart. Air-cured samples should have no loss of Na₂O content and hence can be used as a baseline reference. The Na⁺ concentration in the 35 ppt saline solution may be even higher than that of the geopolymer polymer slurry. Thus, during curing, the Na⁺ in the saline solution may diffuse into the slurry, resulting in an increase in the Na⁺ or Na₂O content in the final geopolymer products. For the samples cured in 0 and 15 ppt saline solutions, their Na₂O contents are all lower than that of the air-cured samples. This is, of course, caused by the diffusion of Na⁺ from the geopolymer slurry into the curing solutions, which have a relatively lower Na⁺ concentration. In summary, during curing, Na⁺ may diffuse into the geopolymer slurry if the curing saline solution has a higher Na⁺ concentration, or out of the geopolymer slurry if the curing solution has a lower Na⁺ concentration.

Further noteworthy are the complex, dynamic chemical exchanges between the hardening-while-being-cured geopolymer slurry and curing solution. This process is further complicated by the potential subsequent leaching of Na⁺ from the hardened geopolymer (e.g., as generally studied by other researchers) as well as the drying of saturated

Fig. 13. Effect of curing condition: (a) percentages of Na₂O in the final geopolymer samples cured under different conditions; (b) saline solution-induced changes in both UCS and Na₂O content.

geopolymer samples, since the latter can result in the precipitation of dissolved salt that is taken into account as the total Na₂O content by the XRF measurements. There are two possible reasons for the even higher Na₂O content in the interior layer of the GC-2.00 cured in 35 ppt saline solution:

- (a) The slightly higher Na₂O content in the interior layer of 35 ppt cured GC-2.00 specimen is simply a measurement error, because the difference between this value and that of the air-cured specimen is very small (i.e., 8.45% vs. 8.56%).
- (b) The chemical exchanges between the curing solution and geopolymer slurry are very complex and dynamic. Whether the Na⁺ cations diffuse into or out of the geopolymer slurry from or into the curing solutions respectively depends upon the Na⁺ concentrations of the geopolymer slurry and the hardened geopolymer. An important factor that needs to be carefully considered and examined is that, during the curing and hardening of geopolymer slurry, the water content may change, and hence the Na⁺ concentration varies with time during this process even under the condition of no chemical exchanges or diffusion. Therefore, another possible explanation to this observed phenomenon is as follows: At the beginning before the geopolymer slurry sets or hardens, Na⁺ cations diffuse into the geopolymer slurry, resulting in an increase in the Na⁺ concentration within the entire geopolymer slurry. Once the geopolymer slurry sets and hardens, the water content decreases, causing an increase in the Na⁺ concentration of the hardened geopolymer and resulting in a higher Na⁺ concentration in the porewater than the curing solution. At

Fig. 14. pH measurements of different curing solutions: (a) pH values before and after curing process; (b) the change in the pH (Δ pH) of the curing solutions (BC = before curing; AC = after curing).

this stage, extra Na⁺ cations in the porewater of the hardened geopolymer start to leach out or diffuse into the curing solution. At the end of curing, the hardened geopolymer has porewater (because the sample is always submerged into solution) that may contain unused Na⁺ cations. Then at the final stage of air-drying, the free Na⁺ cations may precipitate as solid salt, and can be detected by the XRF measurements.

Fig. 13b compares the dependencies of both UCS and the interior layer's Na₂O content on the curing condition for the two different geopolymer samples (i.e., GC-2.00 versus GC-1.78). Clearly, for each condition, the Na₂O content of GC-2.00 is always greater than that of GC-1.78. As such, the former usually has a higher UCS than the latter. Moreover, for each type of geopolymer, the change in the UCS follows the exact same trend as the variation in the Na₂O content. Such a consistency between the two geopolymers points out that the strength development of the underwater cast and cured geopolymers is affected by the chemical exchanges, particularly cations, between the curing solutions and geopolymer slurry. In fact, Na⁺, as an essential cation to balance the insufficient charge of Al³⁺ in the geopolymer's atomic structure [12,21], controls the formation of geopolymer binders and hence the mechanical strength. In summary, the degree of geopolymerization or fraction of geopolymer binder in the final cured geopolymeric product is proportionally mirrored through the variation of Na⁺ or Na₂O content in the geopolymer samples.

3.5. pH measurements

To further prove the exchange (i.e., either leaching or intrusion) of chemicals between the being-cured geopolymer slurry and the curing solution during the period of 28-day's curing, the pH values of different curing solutions for all samples were measured before and after the curing process. To ensure accuracy and comparability, the volume of each curing solution is exactly 150 mL. The 0, 15 and 35 ppt saline solutions have an initial pH 6.97, 8.04, and 8.00, respectively, which remain the same within 24 h. Fig. 14a compares the curing solutions' pH values obtained before and after the curing process for the two types of geopolymers. Clearly, after 28 days of curing, the pH values of all curing solutions increase to different extents. At the same salinity, curing the GC-2.00 samples causes slightly higher increases than curing the GC-1.78 ones, obviously owing to the higher NaOH concentration used in the GC-2.00 synthesis. Fig. 14b compares the pH increment (i.e., ΔpH) for the OWC, GC-1.78, and GC-2.00 samples. For the same curing solution (i.e., the same salinity), OWC induces the largest ΔpH , while the smallest ΔpH is caused by the GC-1.78, but the ΔpH difference between the GC-2.00 and GC-1.78 is not so significant. The most important feature is that the higher the curing solution's salinity, the lower the change in its pH (i.e., ΔpH). The increase in the curing solutions' pH manifests the leaching of OH^- and alkali metal cations from the geopolymer slurry into the solution [29,45], which is consistent with the XRF results discussed earlier. Therefore, according to the principle of chemical equilibrium, a curing solution with a higher salinity or ionic strength can suppress the leaching of OH^- from the slurry into the solution, thus preventing the further reduction in the strength of cured geopolymers.

4. Discussion

4.1. Difference from prior studies

As stated previously, much work has been conducted on the resistance of geopolymers to various chemical solutions. Such resistance involves interactions between the chemical solutions and geopolymers that have been completely cured (e.g., after 28 days of curing) or pre-cured in air to some extent (e.g., the samples at least hardened so that demolding and handling become possible). For example, Giasuddin et al. [30] studied Class F fly ash-based geopolymers with a small fraction of ground granulated blast furnace slag as an additive cured in freshwater and NaCl solutions, and monitored the pH of the different curing media over time. They found that the pH increment was fast at the beginning 2 h upon sample submersion and then became slower after 2 h, but their samples had been first air-cured inside non-permeable molds at room temperature for 10–12 h and then placed in the liquids after demolding, or at least were not underwater casted with the curing starting when the geopolymer was still in a slurry consistency. Thokchom et al. [45] studied the interactions between Class F fly ash-based geopolymer mortars and 10% magnesium sulfate solution by exposing samples that had been air-cured for 28 days to the solution for up to 24 weeks, and found that the increase in pH was rapid during the initial 3 weeks and was not appreciable thereafter. However, a significant difference that distinguishes the current study from others is that the interactions between the geopolymer and curing solutions start immediately after underwater casting. In other words, little or no air-curing/hardening is permitted prior to the submersion of the geopolymer slurry into the curing solution. Such a procedure realistically simulates the actual construction processes, such as injecting cement slurry into the borehole for well cementing or casting in situ concrete slurry under seawater. As such, it should be expected that more chemical exchanges occur between the curing saline solutions and geopolymer slurry than the pre-hardened geopolymer at a greater rate, which is likely to affect the strength development of geopolymers and thus needs to be simulated in laboratory experiments.

4.2. Mechanisms for strength development

Based on the above results, casting and immediate curing in three saline solutions leads to a significant difference in the UCS of the geopolymer and OWC samples. In particular, the OWC's UCS decreases significantly with increasing the solution's salinity, while the geopolymer shows the opposite trend. It is well known that the strength of ordinary Portland cements can be negatively affected by chemicals in the seawater, such as the Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , and Na^+ . Detailed discussion of these effects is not the focus of this paper, but can be found in a plenty of publications, some of which have been summarized earlier.

For geopolymers, although the above results show that curing in saline water can still cause the leaching of OH^- and Na^+ , the amount of leached ions and other chemicals decreases with increasing salinity. As such, when compared with freshwater curing, increasing the curing solution's salinity actually results in an increase in the UCS. In other words, a higher salinity can suppress the leaching of alkali ions (i.e., Na^+ , OH^-) from the slurry, which can influence the development of UCS. Moreover, a beneficial effect is that, if the curing solution has a higher Na^+ concentration than the being-cured geopolymer slurry, Na^+ cations may intrude into the latter, resulting in a higher strength. In addition, geopolymers in general are not prone to chemical attacks or deterioration by Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} , among others. Therefore, the underlying mechanisms for the increase in the UCS of geopolymers cured in saline solutions, when compared with freshwater curing, primarily include the prevention and reduction of leaching of alkali ions from the slurry, and secondarily include the ingress of some beneficial cations such as Na^+ into the slurry when the curing solution's salinity is very high.

4.3. Practical implications

As discussed above, the increase in the UCS of saline water-cured geopolymers with curing salinity demonstrates that a higher salinity, such as 35 ppt, can bring beneficial effects on the mechanical properties of geopolymers. Moreover, the effects of saline water curing on the rate and magnitude of strength are more pronounced for geopolymers with a lower Si/Al molar ratio than those with a higher Si/Al ratio. These findings have significant practical implications for underwater construction that requires in-situ casting concrete slurry directly underwater, particularly in chemically harsh environments such as offshore and underground brine formations. Although special Portland cements (such as the studied oil well cement) can fulfill the functional needs, they are prone to chemical attacks and deterioration, particularly by the high-salinity solutions. However, for geopolymers that have been proven to resist acid and sulfate chemicals, directly casting in high-salinity water actually favors the development of higher mechanical strengths, thus eliminating the need for extra functional additives typically used to improve the durability and resistance of ordinary Portland cement.

A particular noteworthy scenario is the potential application of geopolymers for oil well cementing in brine reservoirs. If ordinary Portland cement were used, the high salinity in the rock formations would require special additives to improve the resistance and durability of Portland cement against salt attacks, particularly at the construction stage when the cement slurry is injected into the gap between steel casing and borehole wall. Otherwise the Portland cement slurry may not reach the desired or designed strength upon curing in brine water. However, for geopolymer slurry, a higher salinity can be beneficial to the strength development of geopolymer slurry, as the higher the salinity, the better the strength development. Based on the above results, a higher Si/Al molar ratio within a certain range can lead to a higher UCS for underwater cast and cured geopolymers due to the less leaching of alkali ions or the intake of some ions from the solution into the slurry.

5. Conclusions

Two types of geopolymers with different Si/Al molar ratios,

synthesized from the mixture of Class C fly ash and metakaolin, were underwater cast and cured in saline solutions of varying salinity. Their mechanical properties, chemical and mineralogical compositions, microstructure, and leaching behavior were characterized. Based on the analysis and comparison of the results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- For the two studied geopolymers (i.e., two Si/Al molar ratios), their UCS increases with the curing solution's salinity, while the OWC exhibits the opposite behavior, with its UCS decreasing in response to increasing salinity. Moreover, although the GC-2.00 geopolymer has a higher UCS than the GC-1.78, the latter shows a higher UCS increment than the former.
- According to the compositional and microstructural analyses, the two completely cured products are both geopolymeric composites, but not pure geopolymers. The final materials comprise a gel-like geopolymer binder as the major matrix, and include nonreactive crystalline phases from raw materials as well as un-reacted or partially-reacted reactive phases. Moreover, immediate curing in saline water can slightly increase the porosity of the outer layer, and leads to non-uniform coloration of the material.
- Upon underwater casting and immediate curing, the geopolymer slurry starts to interact with the curing solution primarily via the exchange of chemicals (i.e., leaching or intrusion). The amount of chemical exchanges may depend upon the rate of geopolymerization reaction (i.e., the hardening or setting). In fact, the leaching out of or intrusion into the slurry and the hardening are two competitive processes that dominate the curing reactions and the performance of the final cured geopolymer.
- The major chemicals exchanged between the geopolymer slurry and curing saline solutions include Na^+ and OH^- , two key ions responsible for the mechanical properties of geopolymer.
- The findings of this study can shed light on the practical applications of geopolymer in chemically harsh environments with additional benefits, such as resistance to chemical attack and enhanced strength resulting from high salinity in the aqueous and subaqueous environments.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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